

On the F.Smarandache function and its mean value

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Abstract For any positive integer n , the famous F.Smarandache function $S(n)$ is defined as the smallest positive integer m such that $n \mid m!$. That is, $S(n) = \min\{m : n \mid m!, n \in N\}$. The main purpose of this paper is using the elementary methods to study a mean value problem involving the F.Smarandache function, and give a sharper asymptotic formula for it.

Keywords F.Smarandache function, mean value, asymptotic formula.

§1. Introduction and result

For any positive integer n , the famous F.Smarandache function $S(n)$ is defined as the smallest positive integer m such that $n \mid m!$. That is, $S(n) = \min\{m : n \mid m!, n \in N\}$. For example, the first few values of $S(n)$ are $S(1) = 1$, $S(2) = 2$, $S(3) = 3$, $S(4) = 4$, $S(5) = 5$, $S(6) = 3$, $S(7) = 7$, $S(8) = 4$, $S(9) = 6$, $S(10) = 5$, \dots . About the elementary properties of $S(n)$, some authors had studied it, and obtained some interesting results, see reference [2], [3] and [4]. For example, Farris Mark and Mitchell Patrick [2] studied the elementary properties of $S(n)$, and gave an estimates for the upper and lower bound of $S(p^\alpha)$. That is, they showed that

$$(p-1)\alpha + 1 \leq S(p^\alpha) \leq (p-1)[\alpha + 1 + \log_p \alpha] + 1.$$

Murthy [3] proved that if n be a prime, then $SL(n) = S(n)$, where $SL(n)$ defined as the smallest positive integer k such that $n \mid [1, 2, \dots, k]$, and $[1, 2, \dots, k]$ denotes the least common multiple of $1, 2, \dots, k$. Simultaneously, Murthy [3] also proposed the following problem:

$$SL(n) = S(n), \quad S(n) \neq n ? \tag{1}$$

Le Maohua [4] completely solved this problem, and proved the following conclusion:

Every positive integer n satisfying (1) can be expressed as

$$n = 12 \quad \text{or} \quad n = p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \cdots p_r^{\alpha_r} p,$$

where p_1, p_2, \dots, p_r, p are distinct primes, and $\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \dots, \alpha_r$ are positive integers satisfying $p > p_i^{\alpha_i}$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, r$.

Dr. Xu Zhefeng [5] studied the value distribution problem of $S(n)$, and proved the following conclusion:

Let $P(n)$ denotes the largest prime factor of n , then for any real number $x > 1$, we have the asymptotic formula

$$\sum_{n \leq x} (S(n) - P(n))^2 = \frac{2\zeta\left(\frac{3}{2}\right) x^{\frac{3}{2}}}{3 \ln x} + O\left(\frac{x^{\frac{3}{2}}}{\ln^2 x}\right),$$

where $\zeta(s)$ denotes the Riemann zeta-function.

On the other hand, Lu Yaming [6] studied the solutions of an equation involving the F.Smarandache function $S(n)$, and proved that for any positive integer $k \geq 2$, the equation

$$S(m_1 + m_2 + \dots + m_k) = S(m_1) + S(m_2) + \dots + S(m_k)$$

has infinite groups positive integer solutions (m_1, m_2, \dots, m_k) .

Jozsef Sandor [7] proved for any positive integer $k \geq 2$, there exist infinite groups positive integer solutions (m_1, m_2, \dots, m_k) satisfied the following inequality:

$$S(m_1 + m_2 + \dots + m_k) > S(m_1) + S(m_2) + \dots + S(m_k).$$

Also, there exist infinite groups of positive integer solutions (m_1, m_2, \dots, m_k) such that

$$S(m_1 + m_2 + \dots + m_k) < S(m_1) + S(m_2) + \dots + S(m_k).$$

The main purpose of this paper is using the elementary and analytic methods to study the mean value properties of $[S(n) - S(S(n))]^2$, and give an interesting mean value formula for it. That is, we shall prove the following conclusion:

Theorem. Let k be any fixed positive integer. Then for any real number $x > 2$, we have the asymptotic formula

$$\sum_{n \leq x} [S(n) - S(S(n))]^2 = \frac{2}{3} \cdot \zeta\left(\frac{3}{2}\right) \cdot x^{\frac{3}{2}} \cdot \sum_{i=1}^k \frac{c_i}{\ln^i x} + O\left(\frac{x^{\frac{3}{2}}}{\ln^{k+1} x}\right),$$

where $\zeta(s)$ is the Riemann zeta-function, c_i ($i = 1, 2, \dots, k$) are computable constants and $c_1 = 1$.

§2. Proof of the Theorem

In this section, we shall prove our theorem directly. In fact for any positive integer $n > 1$, let $n = p_1^{\alpha_1} p_2^{\alpha_2} \dots p_s^{\alpha_s}$ be the factorization of n into prime powers, then from [3] we know that

$$S(n) = \max\{S(p_1^{\alpha_1}), S(p_2^{\alpha_2}), \dots, S(p_s^{\alpha_s})\} \equiv S(p^\alpha). \tag{2}$$

Now we consider the summation

$$\sum_{n \leq x} [S(n) - S(S(n))]^2 = \sum_{n \in A} [S(n) - S(S(n))]^2 + \sum_{n \in B} [S(n) - S(S(n))]^2, \tag{3}$$

where A and B denote the subsets of all positive integer in the interval $[1, x]$. A denotes the set involving all integers $n \in [1, x]$ such that $S(n) = S(p^2)$ for some prime p ; B denotes the set involving all integers $n \in [1, x]$ such that $S(n) = S(p^\alpha)$ with $\alpha = 1$ or $\alpha \geq 3$. If $n \in A$, then $n = p^2m$ with $P(m) < 2p$, where $P(m)$ denotes the largest prime factor of m . So from the definition of $S(n)$ we have $S(n) = S(mp^2) = S(p^2) = 2p$ and $S(S(n)) = S(2p) = p$ if $p > 2$.

From (2) and the definition of A we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \sum_{n \in A} [S(n) - S(S(n))]^2 \\
 = & \sum_{\substack{n \leq x \\ p^2 \parallel n, \sqrt{n} < p^2}} [S(p^2) - S(S(p^2))]^2 + \sum_{\substack{n \leq x \\ p^2 \parallel n, p^2 \leq \sqrt{n}}} [S(p^2) - S(S(p^2))]^2 \\
 = & \sum_{\substack{p^2 n \leq x \\ n < p^2, (p, n)=1}} [S(p^2) - S(S(p^2))]^2 + \sum_{\substack{p^2 n \leq x \\ p^2 \leq n, (p, n)=1}} [S(p^2) - S(S(p^2))]^2 \\
 = & \sum_{\substack{p^2 n \leq x \\ n < p^2, (p, n)=1}} p^2 + \sum_{\substack{p^2 n \leq x \\ n \geq p^2, (p, n)=1}} p^2 + O(1) \\
 = & \sum_{n \leq \sqrt{x}} \sum_{n < p^2 \leq \frac{x}{n}} p^2 + O\left(\sum_{m \leq x^{\frac{1}{4}}} \sum_{p \leq (\frac{x}{m})^{\frac{1}{3}}} p^2\right) + O\left(\sum_{p \leq x^{\frac{1}{4}}} \sum_{p^2 \leq n \leq \frac{x}{p^2}} p^2\right) \\
 = & \sum_{n \leq \sqrt{x}} \sum_{p \leq \sqrt{\frac{x}{n}}} p^2 + O\left(\frac{x^{\frac{5}{4}}}{\ln x}\right), \tag{4}
 \end{aligned}$$

where $p^2 \parallel n$ denotes $p^2 | n$ and $p^3 \nmid n$.

By the Abel's summation formula (See Theorem 4.2 of [8]) and the Prime Theorem (See Theorem 3.2 of [9]):

$$\pi(x) = \sum_{i=1}^k \frac{a_i \cdot x}{\ln^i x} + O\left(\frac{x}{\ln^{k+1} x}\right),$$

where a_i ($i = 1, 2, \dots, k$) are computable constants and $a_1 = 1$.

We have

$$\begin{aligned}
 \sum_{p \leq \sqrt{\frac{x}{n}}} p^2 &= \frac{x}{n} \cdot \pi\left(\sqrt{\frac{x}{n}}\right) - \int_{\frac{3}{2}}^{\sqrt{\frac{x}{n}}} 2y \cdot \pi(y) dy \\
 &= \frac{1}{3} \cdot \frac{x^{\frac{3}{2}}}{n^{\frac{3}{2}}} \cdot \sum_{i=1}^k \frac{b_i}{\ln^i \sqrt{\frac{x}{n}}} + O\left(\frac{x^{\frac{3}{2}}}{n^{\frac{3}{2}} \cdot \ln^{k+1} x}\right), \tag{5}
 \end{aligned}$$

where we have used the estimate $n \leq \sqrt{x}$, and all b_i are computable constants and $b_1 = 1$.

Note that $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^{\frac{3}{2}}} = \zeta\left(\frac{3}{2}\right)$, and $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\ln^i n}{n^{\frac{3}{2}}}$ is convergent for all $i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, k$. So from

(4) and (5) we have

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \sum_{n \in A} [S(n) - S(S(n))]^2 \\
 &= \sum_{n \leq \sqrt{x}} \left[\frac{1}{3} \cdot \frac{x^{\frac{3}{2}}}{n^{\frac{3}{2}}} \cdot \sum_{i=1}^k \frac{b_i}{\ln^i \sqrt{\frac{x}{n}}} + O\left(\frac{x^{\frac{3}{2}}}{n^{\frac{3}{2}} \cdot \ln^{k+1} x}\right) \right] + O\left(\frac{x^{\frac{5}{4}}}{\ln x}\right) \\
 &= \frac{2}{3} \cdot \zeta\left(\frac{3}{2}\right) \cdot x^{\frac{3}{2}} \cdot \sum_{i=1}^k \frac{c_i}{\ln^i x} + O\left(\frac{x^{\frac{3}{2}}}{\ln^{k+1} x}\right), \tag{6}
 \end{aligned}$$

where c_i ($i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, k$) are computable constants and $c_1 = 1$.

Now we estimate the summation in set B . For any positive integer $n \in B$, if $S(n) = S(p) = p$, then $[S(n) - S(S(n))]^2 = [S(p) - S(S(p))]^2 = 0$; If $S(n) = S(p^\alpha)$ with $\alpha \geq 3$, then

$$[S(n) - S(S(n))]^2 = [S(p^\alpha) - S(S(p^\alpha))]^2 \leq \alpha^2 p^2$$

and $\alpha \leq \ln x$. So that we have

$$\sum_{n \in B} [S(n) - S(S(n))]^2 \ll \sum_{\substack{np^\alpha \leq x \\ \alpha \geq 3}} \alpha^2 \cdot p^2 \ll x \cdot \ln^2 x. \tag{7}$$

Combining (3), (6) and (7) we may immediately deduce the asymptotic formula

$$\sum_{n \leq x} [S(n) - S(S(n))]^2 = \frac{2}{3} \cdot \zeta\left(\frac{3}{2}\right) \cdot x^{\frac{3}{2}} \cdot \sum_{i=1}^k \frac{c_i}{\ln^i x} + O\left(\frac{x^{\frac{3}{2}}}{\ln^{k+1} x}\right),$$

where c_i ($i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, k$) are computable constants and $c_1 = 1$.

This completes the proof of Theorem.

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